

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

UNESCO Chair in
ICT for Development
Royal Holloway, University of London

Guidance Note

Annex 4

From the Report: Education for the most marginalised post-COVID-19: Guidance for governments on the use of digital technologies in education
ACT THREE (OF THREE): GUIDANCE NOTES

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EdTech Hub

Clear evidence, better decisions, more learning.

Report homepage <https://edtechhub.org/education-for-the-most-marginalised-post-covid-19/>

Annex 4

Examples of infographics and slide-decks that can be developed based on the guidance notes in *Act Three*¹

Infographics

Digital technologies and girls' education

GUIDANCE NOTE

Digital technologies and girls' education

Education for the Most Marginalised post-Covid-19: a guide for governments

8 PRINCIPLES

- PROVIDE EQUAL ACCESS TO DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES**
Governments should ensure that girls have as equal access to digital technologies (both devices and content) as do boys throughout the education system.
- PROTECT GIRLS AND WOMEN**
Governments should ensure that there is appropriate legislation, enforcement and guidance to help protect girls and women from all forms of abuse, bullying and harassment through digital technologies.
- FOCUS EXPLICITLY ON CULTURALLY SPECIFICALLY WAYS TO EMPOWER GIRLS**
Governments should focus explicitly on culturally specifically ways through which they can empower girls to become informed and proactive agents of future social and technological change.
- COLLECT GENDER DISAGGREGATED DATA**
Governments should ensure that they collect gender disaggregated data with respect to digital technologies, so that they can accurately monitor changes in gender digital inequality.
- EXAMINE MEN'S ATTITUDES TOWARDS WOMEN AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES**
Governments should ensure that they put in place effective initiatives to change men's attitudes towards women and digital technologies; emphasis should not be placed simply on providing programmes to support girls and women in technology.
- ENCOURAGE EDUCATION TO BE SEEN AS A COLLECTIVE AND NETWORKED EXPERIENCE**
Governments should encourage education to be seen as a collective and networked experience, in which learners, parents, guardians, educators and facilitators all have important roles to play, and all of whom require appropriate digital access and skills training.
- CRITICALLY EXAMINE ANY DIGITAL "SOLUTIONS" FOR GIRLS**
Be careful and selective in choosing the most relevant and appropriate digital "solutions" for girls. There are very many organisations offering digital "solutions" for girls' education, and great care is needed in selecting those that are most relevant and appropriate for girls and women in your own context.
- USE EXAMPLES OF SUCCESSFUL WOMEN IN ALL EDUCATION CONTENT**
Examples of successful women should be used appropriately in all educational content. Women scientists, for example, should be shown as often as men scientists in textbooks and online content.

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¹ All graphics designed by Alicjia Pawluczuk.

GUIDANCE NOTE

Involving marginalised young people in the design of their own education

Education for the Most Marginalised post-Covid-19: a guide for governments

5 PRINCIPLES

There are five principles essential for governments who wish to create education systems that engage effectively with the learners for which they are intended.

1

DESIGN WITH RATHER THAN FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

All aspects of digital learning, including platforms, access and content, should be designed *with* rather than *for* young people.

2

ADDRESS THE NEEDS OF FORMAL AND INFORMAL LEARNING

Governments should design specific programmes to develop learners' voices, contributions and responsibilities as a continual process not only within schools, but also in informal learning settings.

3

REMEMBER ABOUT THE IMPORTANCE OF TEAM WORK

Young people learn much from each other. Hence, they should be encouraged to work in teams when using digital technologies, to encourage mutual assistance, support and responsibility.

4

CONSIDER THE ROLE OF PEER-TO-PEER LEARNING

It is essential to have resilient systems in place that encourage and support peer-to-peer learning and collaboration, especially during times of crisis.

5

NURTURE AND SUSTAIN MEANINGFUL PARTNERSHIPS

Partnerships that involve civil society can help bridge the gap between government priorities, private sector approaches, communities and the needs and interests of young people.

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Slide decks

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There has long been growing concern about the imbalances between men and women's access to digital technologies, and their engagement in the tech sector at all levels.

#EMMpostcovid19 01

Digital technologies and girls' education

The digital gender divide represent far deeper social and cultural structures, and unless these are changed the increasing use of digital technologies – as accelerators – will serve to increase rather than reduce such inequalities.

#EMMpostcovid19 02

This guidance note encourages governments to adopt a two-pronged approach:

To focus specifically on ways through which digital technologies can themselves serve to include rather than exclude girls and women in education

To address the wider issues surrounding the involvement of women in the tech sector.

#EMMpostcovid19 03

The guidance below focuses on the most important first steps that governments can take specifically to reduce gender digital inequalities in learning through digital technologies, and also to encourage the wider engagement of women in the science and technology sectors.

#EMMpostcovid19 04

<p>Governments should ensure that girls have as equal access to digital technologies (both devices and content) as do boys throughout the education system.</p>	<p>2</p> <p>#EMMpostcovid19</p>		
<p>Governments should focus explicitly on culturally specific ways through which they can empower girls to become informed and proactive agents of future social and technological change.</p>	<p>4</p> <p>#EMMpostcovid19</p>		
<p>Governments should ensure that they put in place effective initiatives to change men's attitudes towards women and digital technologies; emphasis should not be placed simply on providing programmes to support girls and women in technology.</p>	<p>6</p> <p>#EMMpostcovid19</p>		
<p>Be careful and selective in choosing the most relevant and appropriate digital "solutions" for girls.</p> <p>There are very many organisations offering digital "solutions" for girls' education, and great care is needed in selecting those that are most relevant and appropriate for girls and women in your own context.</p>	<p>8</p> <p>#EMMpostcovid19</p>		

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